

EFFECT OF BARIUM SULFATE NANOPARTICLES WITH ORGANIC ALCOHOL ON THE IONIZING RADIATION SHIELDING

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Abstract: In this paper, we will discuss how to make manufacture shielding and measure the attenuation coefficient of gamma rays, which is one of the most important points of protection from ionizing radiation. To make the shield, we will use Barium sulfate (BaSO_4) nano powder as reinforcement at different concentrations (10%, 20%, 30%, 40%) and then mix PMMA liquid, then slowly stir for several minutes to reduce air bubble containment. Then we calculate the linear and mass attenuation coefficient of the shield (BaSO_4 - PMMA) as well as the effective atomic number, the density of the composite material and the value of the electronic density. At different concentrations, thicknesses and energies. It is clear that with the increase in the concentration of the reinforcement materials, the values of the linear and mass attenuation coefficients also increased. as well as with the increase in the concentration of the materials, the value of the effective atomic number and the electronic density increased.

Introduction:

Humans are exposed to different types of radiation due to the tremendous development in the fields of nuclear technology and their applications in the field of medicine, agriculture and industry. This has resulted in the buildup of large quantities of radioactive waste, different radiation level, which caused exposure of humans and the surrounding environment to radiation hazards. So it became necessary to maintain the safety of workers, the working environment, and protecting humanity from exposure to such radiation. Shields are used depending on the type of radiation Shields are used depending on the type of radiation (neutron, gamma, beta, alpha) where the use of radiation source in this study isotopes gamma rays. It is known that the traditional shields of gamma radiation uses lead which has properties of high atomic number and high density in addition to it is expensive as well as toxic. Due to the technological development in the material world, there is a great interest among researchers in this field by searching from overlapping materials to come a desirable solution to solve shielding problems and alternative to traditional materials And we used materials with a physiological specification has the ability to absorb radiation, and these materials, the tungsten oxide, which has a high atomic number and high density close to the density of lead and there are several studies that used metal materials reinforced with epoxy, which has several applications, including industrial, health and research.[1,2]

Literature Review:

Since gamma ray have been used in many fields such as medicine, industry, agriculture and nuclear physics research, several studies have been done in regarding of the attenuation of photons; however, the manufacture of shielding with high more quality, higher attenuation coefficient is challenge. Here in this section the review some studies interested in this field have been stated as following:

In Mohamed et al., have been studied the attenuating properties of some (Ag-Cu-Sn Alloys) by using the Nation Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) XCOM code in the energy range (0.01 to 10 MeV [3].

In Aldhuhaibat et al., have been studied the linear attenuation coefficients μ , the mean free path, the half value layer, the tenth value layer and Penetration depth values for composite shields from epoxy with (Cement, Al, Fe and Pb), they shown

E+Pb.Fe.Al. Cement shield which proved the availability for using this composite shield as a suitable shield of gamma-ray [4].

In Chang et al., prepared Tungsten/epoxy composites by blending epoxy resin with different weight percent of tungsten powder. They investigated the effect of filler loading on shielding and mechanical properties of composites was investigated by using two different activities of Co-60 source. They showed that with the increase of tungsten loading, shielding property of composites increases. However, with the increase of irradiation dose, thermal stability and mechanical properties of composites decrease firstly, then increase slightly, and decline sharply at the end due to competition reaction between chain scission and cross-linking originated from γ -ray radiation [5].

In Osman et al., studied the shielding properties of polymer composites using neutrons and gamma rays emitted from Cf-252 neutron source. Polymer composites with different Aluminum oxide percentage (0, 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 wt. %) have been prepared. They founded macroscopic cross-section Σ_R (cm^{-1}) and the total attenuation coefficients μ (cm^{-1}) for total gamma rays. The displayed results indicated that the constructed materials show good radiation protection properties [6].

In Aral et al., used tungsten, bismuth, tin, and copper powders were used as additives in the fabric coating to obtain lead-free and flexible x-ray shielding material. They showed that tungsten additives in silicone rubber coating had better attenuation ratios than the samples that contain tungsten–tin, bismuth, and tungsten–copper, at same additive volume ratios. [7] .

In Erol et al., used high-density polyethylene, boron carbide, and wolfram carbide can be mixed in certain amounts and composite discs can be obtained. They suggested a new shielding material is efficient for gamma radiation [8].

In Ran et al., fabricated Epoxy resin matrix composites filled with dispersed micro and nano gadolinium oxide (Gd_2O_3) particles of different contents. The gamma radiation shielding and mechanical properties of these micro and nano composites were evaluated by measuring mass attenuation coefficients at photon energies from 31 keV to 356 keV and flexural performances. The reason is attributed to higher probability of interaction between γ -ray and nano particles. Especially, this effect is prominent in low particle concentration. For flexural property, nano- Gd_2O_3 /epoxy composite show equivalent flexural strength and up to 15 % higher flexural modulus compared with micro- Gd_2O_3 /epoxy composite. Based on these experimental results, nano- Gd_2O_3 reinforced epoxy composite is believed to be a promising novel radiation shielding material [9].

The aim of the Study:

In spite of its high density of lead as example, which mostly used as a shielding material to protect the human from the radiation, however, it is toxic and very heavy for personal shielding. Due to the

development in the field of production safety materials and requirement used in medical, industrial and research. In this study, the technical nanotechnology of the composite materials in the manufacture of high efficiency protective nuclear shields. However, it is important to suggest a new materials nontoxic, light, and environmentally friendly as a shielding from ionization radiation. Since Polymers alone is not effective to protect from radiation, so this work suggested to study the values of the linear and mass attenuation coefficients, effective atomic numbers and electronic densities of the composite material.

Introduction:

The photoelectric effect, the Compton scattering and the pair production processes are the predominant interactions between the photons and atoms apart from other types over a wide range of energies. With wide spread utilization of radiation and radioisotopes in medicine, industry and basic sciences, the problem of radiation protection has become important aspect while handling radiation sources and radiation generating equipments. Selection of materials for radiation shielding and protection needs accurate assessment of interaction parameters. These parameters are of immense importance for photons being highly penetrating radiation as compared to particulate radiations. A survey of other relevant measurements [1-12] reported shows that in many of these measurements the experimental results for the same elements at the same energies are somewhat inconsistent. Appreciable discrepancies between the experimental and theoretical values were observed in some of these measurements. In view of this situation a series of accurate and consistent measurements of gamma-ray mass attenuation coefficients was undertaken by author. The results of these measurements covering Al element at three photon energies. A possible effect due to multiply scattered photons from thick attenuators on the measurements has been minimized to a great extent by using extremely –narrow-beam collimation and selected attenuator thicknesses.

$$I = I_0 e^{-\mu * x} \quad \dots (1)$$

Where I_0 represents the incident ray intensity when measured without shield, I represents ray intensity transmitted through the thickness shield (x) [38-40].

Where $\mu(cm^{-1})$ is the linear attenuation coefficient, since this coefficient depends on the density of the absorbent material, so it was necessary to know the mass attenuation coefficient (μ_m) which indicates the probability of interaction with the unit of mass of the material, Linear attenuation coefficient by the following equation [16]: -

$$\mu_m \left(\frac{cm^2}{gm} \right) = \frac{\mu(cm^{-1})}{\rho} \quad \dots (2)$$

Effective atomic number and electron density (Z_{eff} , N_e)

The effective atomic number is one of the important parameters of the interaction of the photon with the matter. It enters into many fields of technology and engineering, in the case of the composite material we see that the atomic number cannot be represented by the correct value as with the elements, but is a quantitative quantity called the effective atomic number that was calculated depending on the participation of each element in the composite material [52-54]. The effective atomic number of the composite material was calculated using the following equations

$$\sigma_m = \mu_m \frac{\sum_i n_i A_i}{N_A} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\sigma_a = \frac{\sigma_m}{\sum_i n_i} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\sigma_e = \frac{1}{N_A} \sum_i \frac{f_i A_i}{Z_i} \mu_i \quad \dots (5)$$

$$Z_{matrix} = \frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_e} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$Z_{eff} = \sum_{i=1}^2 w_i Z_i \quad \dots (7)$$

$$N_e = \frac{\mu_m}{\sigma_e} \quad \dots (8)$$

Where n_i : The number of atom each element in the base material, A_i : are the mass number of each element in the base material, N_A : is Avogadro's number, σ_m the molecular cross section, σ_a : the atomic cross section, f_i : is the fractional abundance of element i : with respect to the number of atoms, Z_i : the atomic number of each element in the base material, σ_e : the electronic cross-section, Z_{matrix} : the atomic number of polymer and w_i : weight fraction shield material.

Weights calculations

For the purpose of manufacturing a composite material consisting of two materials, it is necessary to make calculations of the weight fracture of the reinforcement materials, and calculate the weight fractions through the following relationship [55]:

$$\psi = \frac{W_f}{W_c} 100\% \quad \dots (9)$$

$$W_c = W_f + W_m \quad \dots (10)$$

ψ : The weight fracture, W_c : The weight of composite material, W_m : The weight of the base material, W_f : Weight of material reinforcement. As for the volumetric fracture, its calculation depends on the weight fraction of each additive ratio and the density of both the base material and the reinforcement material, as in the following relationship [56]:

$$V_f = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1-\psi}{\psi} \cdot \frac{\rho_f}{\rho_m}} \quad \dots (11)$$

Whereas ρ_f : Density of the reinforcement material, ρ_m : Density of the base material:

V_f : Volumetric fracture of composite material. Therefore, the density of the composite material is [57]: -

$$\rho_c = V_f \rho_f + (1 - V_f) \rho_m \quad \dots (12)$$

Method of Shields Preparation:

The pre-polymerized PMMA beads, Barium sulfate Nano powder (Baso4) as reinforcement in different concentrations (10%, 20%, 30%, 40%) were mixed together and poured into the PMMA monomer liquid, then stirred slowly for several minutes to reduce the inclusion of the air bubble. The mixing process takes place with a mechanical fan, then it is transferred to an ultrasound machine to complete the mixing process through this device and for a period of time, after that the mixed solutions were poured into certain molds.

Counting system:

Includes a brief description of the electronic counting and analysis system using the Sodium Iodide doped Thallium detector NaI(Tl) was used with (2"x2") for ORTEC program (Scintivision-Buffer) with an integrated measuring system have been used as electronic system , with detailed engineering arrangements for the best practical results, measurement and analysis steps Figs (3-1),(3-2) shown spectrum Cs-137 and Co-60 , the time collecting for Co-60 (1 hour) and Cs-137(20 min).

Scintillation Detectors (Model 802):

Using the Sodium iodide doped thallium detector NaI (Tl) with (2"x2") which is Highly efficient and required for gamma-ray detection. It also has the high stability of the accompanying electronic devices.

Figure (1): Cs-137 spectrum

Figure (2): Co-60 spectrum.

The Digi BASE:

The Digi BASE is a 14-pin photomultiplier tube base for gamma-ray spectroscopy applications with NaI (Tl) scintillation detectors. The unique concept of the Digi BASE combines a miniaturized preamplifier and detector high voltage (0 to +1200 V bias) with powerful digital signal processing, multichannel analyzer,

and special features for fine time resolution measurements all contained in a low-power (<500 mA), lightweight (280 g), small-size (63 mm diameter x 80 mm length) tube base with a USB connection. Everything you need to connect to your NaI (Tl) detector is included in the tube base. Furthermore, there is no need to open your computer to install an interface card, or for using external NIM-based components. The digiBASE includes MAESTRO-32 MCA emulation software and is available with ScintiVision-32 for complete quantitative analysis.

Figure (3): Schematic diagram of experimental setup.

Results and Discussion:

The results and discussion of the shielding parameters and explanation of the behavior of these parameters. Effect of concentration of armor reinforcement material. On these properties are the coefficients of linear and mass attenuation, the effective atomic numbers and the electronic density of the composite material. As shown in Table (4-1), the values of the effective atomic number of shields were calculated using equation (2-16). Explains the relationship. It can be seen that the increasing atomic number increases with increasing concentration of the compound substance. This can be explained by an increase in the concentration of additives, which leads to an increase in the number of atomic shields, that is, there is an improvement in the properties of the epoxy towards the properties of the reinforcing material. Therefore, by increasing the concentration of the reinforcing materials, it is possible to obtain a large atomic substance that makes it suitable for use as a shield against gamma rays. Figure (4-32) shows the relationship between the atomic effect and the concentration of the additive. The density of the shields was calculated using equation (2-20), where the effect of the concentration of reinforcement materials on the density of the shield material was studied for concentration. Which can be illustrated as in Figure (4-2) that the density of the shield material increases with increasing concentration, and the probability of gamma rays interacting with the high-density shield It is greater than the probability of its interaction with the shield and the density slows down. This means that the adsorption processes will increase due to the increase in the distribution of the reinforcing materials in the base material, which leads to the linear and mass attenuation coefficients of the gamma rays of the manufactured shield. Which can be illustrated as in Figure (4-3). The electronic density of the fabricated shield material can be calculated through equation (4-18) through the results. We note that with the increase in the concentration of the reinforcement material, the mass attenuation coefficient increases due to the increase in the cross-section of the shield material, meaning that the interaction of gamma photons with the fabricated shield material increases, so the density of electrons per unit mass will It increases Which can be illustrated as in Figure (4-4).

Table (1) the values of the linear and mass attenuation coefficients, effective atomic numbers and electronic densities of the composite material.

Concentration of reinforcement (%)	Concentration of Polymer (%)	μ_e	μ_m	ρ_{cop}	Z_{eff}	N_e
10	90	0.11765	0.096119	1.224	4.44059	0.258038
20	80	0.13447	0.103518	1.299	6.83608	0.277901
30	70	0.15293	0.11018	1.388	9.23157	0.295786
40	60	0.17545	0.118788	1.477	11.62706	0.318894

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